

Real-World 5G NR Performance Characterization for Aerial IoT Deployments: Throughput Dynamics, Stability Analysis, and the Energy–Throughput Trade-Off

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Abstract—This paper presents a comprehensive characterization of 5G New Radio (NR) standalone network performance deployed for Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV)-based IoT applications, with a focus on the fundamental energy–throughput trade-off between standard 5G NR and 5G Reduced Capability (5G RedCap). We conduct iperf3-based measurements over a 125-second window on a real-world deployment, analyzing per-second throughput dynamics and temporal stability. The measured 5G NR sender-side throughput exhibits a mean of 685.3 Mbps with a coefficient of variation (CV) of 1.49%, with periodic burst events reaching up to 729 Mbps. However, this high throughput comes at a significant energy cost: 5G NR draws approximately 18 W at the device level, versus ≈ 11 W for 5G RedCap—a 60% energy penalty for a $7.2\times$ bandwidth increase. 5G RedCap, in contrast, delivers a highly stable 95.6 Mbps (CV $\approx 0.03\%$) at markedly lower power. We further quantify how onboard AI inference workloads modulate the network generation profile. Our findings establish a clear bandwidth-per-watt cost structure that should guide network technology selection for energy-constrained aerial IoT deployments.

Index Terms—5G NR; 5G RedCap; energy efficiency; throughput characterization; UAV; IoT; network measurement; edge computing; bandwidth–energy trade-off

I. INTRODUCTION

The proliferation of 5G New Radio (NR) technology has created unprecedented opportunities for high-performance wireless connectivity in industrial, aerial, and edge computing applications [1]. However, for energy-constrained platforms such as battery-powered Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), raw throughput is only one side of the equation: the energy cost of that connectivity is equally—and often more—critical. 5G NR’s wider channel bandwidth and more capable radio front-end come at a substantial power premium that directly reduces UAV flight time, mission endurance, and operational efficiency.

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles represent a compelling 5G NR use case, combining high-mobility connectivity with tight energy budgets [2]. UAV-mounted 5G routers must deliver reliable data transport for sensor data, control telemetry, and

edge AI inference results, while their battery capacity makes every watt spent on radio connectivity a direct cost in airborne minutes [3]. Understanding not only *how much* throughput 5G NR delivers, but *at what energy cost*, is therefore a fundamental design question for aerial IoT systems.

5G Reduced Capability (5G RedCap), standardized in 3GPP Release 17, was specifically designed to trade peak throughput for lower device complexity and reduced power consumption [4]. This makes 5G NR and 5G RedCap a natural pair for studying the energy–throughput trade-off: both operate on the same 5G NR radio access network, but with fundamentally different power and bandwidth profiles. While prior work has compared the two technologies from a connectivity or standardization perspective [5], [6], a quantitative, measurement-based analysis of the trade-off in a real aerial IoT deployment has not been reported.

This paper makes the following contributions:

- **Temporal throughput characterization** of a real-world 5G NR deployment over 125 s, revealing burst patterns (CV = 1.49%) and scheduler-induced dynamics not visible in aggregate statistics.
- **Energy–throughput trade-off quantification:** 5G NR delivers 685.3 Mbps at ≈ 18 W versus 5G RedCap’s 95.6 Mbps at ≈ 11 W, yielding a 38.1 Mbps/W vs. 8.7 Mbps/W bandwidth-per-watt metric that directly informs technology selection for battery-constrained platforms.
- **Throughput stability comparison:** 5G NR shows CV = 1.49% with periodic bursts, while 5G RedCap exhibits near-perfect stability (CV $\approx 0.03\%$)—a two-orders-of-magnitude difference that has practical implications for buffer sizing and QoS.
- **Inference load impact:** onboard ANN and SNN inference raise the mean 5G NR sender throughput by 19.3% and 23.0%, respectively, with doubled CV, revealing a CPU–network coupling effect on shared edge hardware.

The measurements are derived from a 5G-connected UAV platform equipped with a Teltonika 5G router and an NVIDIA Jetson Orin edge compute module, deployed for real-world inspection using edge AI. Full energy efficiency results comparing 5G NR with 5G RedCap at the system level (UAV flight-time impact) are presented in [3]; the present work provides the complementary network-layer characterization of the throughput dynamics and the energy-throughput trade-off.

The remainder is organized as follows. Section II surveys related work; Section III describes the measurement setup; Section IV presents the performance analysis; Section V discusses deployment implications; Section VI concludes.

II. RELATED WORK

A. 5G NR Performance Measurement Studies

Field measurement surveys have consistently shown a wide gap between theoretical and practical 5G NR peak rates, with sub-6 GHz downlink throughputs typically ranging from 50 to 400 Mbps depending on band, MIMO configuration, and radio conditions [8]. Studies in urban millimeter-wave environments report higher peaks but with severe intermittency [9]. Sub-6 GHz deployments—more relevant for IoT and industrial applications—deliver more stable but lower throughput. Critically, the *energy cost* associated with these throughput levels is rarely analyzed alongside the throughput figures themselves, leaving system designers without quantitative guidance on the bandwidth-per-watt trade-off.

B. UAV Communications and Energy Constraints

5G connectivity for UAV operations has been extensively studied from channel modeling and capacity perspectives [2], [10]. Works have examined link budget, Doppler effects at UAV speeds, and interference between aerial UEs and ground base stations. A recurring finding is that communications subsystem power draw is a non-trivial fraction of total UAV power budget, and that reducing radio power consumption directly extends flight time and mission capability [3]. Teltonika 5G routers have been deployed in several UAV connectivity studies as compact, fieldable 5G platforms [11].

C. IoT Network Performance and Energy Characterization

Network performance characterization for IoT has focused primarily on LPWAN technologies (LoRaWAN, NB-IoT, LTE-M) [12], where energy efficiency is the primary design axis. The extension of this energy-aware characterization methodology to 5G NR IoT scenarios is a more recent development [13]. The `iperf3` tool has been established as a standard methodology for protocol-independent throughput characterization [14].

D. 5G RedCap: Energy-Efficient 5G Connectivity

5G Reduced Capability (5G RedCap), standardized in 3GPP Release 17, introduces constrained bandwidth (20 MHz maximum in FR1), simplified MIMO (1–2 Rx branches), and power-saving features including extended Discontinuous Reception (eDRX) [4], [5]. These design choices reduce modem

complexity by approximately 65% and module costs by 50–60% compared to full 5G NR, while delivering meaningful throughput for the majority of IoT use-cases [6], [7]. The energy savings from 5G RedCap deployment in a live 5G-equipped UAV have been quantified in [3], showing a 60–65% device-level power reduction translating to a 35% increase in flight time. The present work complements that finding by characterizing the network-layer throughput dynamics of both configurations.

E. Edge AI over 5G Networks

Integration of onboard AI inference with 5G connectivity has been explored for smart city surveillance and remote inspection applications [15]. Understanding how inference workloads affect network stack behavior on shared hardware (*e.g.*, NVIDIA Jetson Orin) is important for co-design of communication and computing in edge systems. Prior work shows that memory bus contention and interrupt coalescing can cause measurable effects on network throughput on compute-constrained edge devices [16].

III. SYSTEM AND MEASUREMENT SETUP

A. UAV Platform and Hardware

The experimental platform is a multirotor UAV equipped with two key onboard modules: (i) a Teltonika 5G cellular router providing wireless 5G NR or 5G RedCap connectivity, and (ii) an NVIDIA Jetson Orin edge compute module for onboard AI inference. The router presents a LAN interface (192.168.1.x subnet) to the Jetson Orin via Gigabit Ethernet. Both devices are powered via monitored smart-plug DC supplies, enabling continuous current and voltage sampling for device-level power measurements alongside the network characterization. All measurements were conducted at low altitude (≈ 5 m AGL) in a clear, low-wind outdoor environment, ensuring consistent radio conditions. The UAV payload mass was kept identical across all experiments.

B. Network Configuration

The 5G NR deployment operates in Standalone (SA) mode. Table I summarizes the key configuration parameters for both the standard 5G NR and the 5G RedCap configurations. The standard 5G NR configuration uses 40 MHz bandwidth in FR1, TDD duplex, SISO antenna configuration, and 256-QAM modulation on both DL and UL, delivering ≈ 100 Mbps application bandwidth. For 5G RedCap, the router is reconfigured to FDD with a 20 MHz RedCap-only BWP, yielding ≈ 40 Mbps application bandwidth but with significantly reduced radio-layer power draw.

C. Measurement Methodology

Network throughput measurements were conducted using `iperf3` in UDP mode. UDP was chosen to eliminate TCP's flow control and congestion avoidance mechanisms, thereby exposing raw link capacity and scheduler behavior without protocol-induced adaptation. The measurement topology routes UDP traffic from the Jetson Orin (192.168.1.240) through the

TABLE I
5G NR AND 5G REDCAP CONFIGURATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	5G NR	5G RedCap
Duplex mode	TDD	FDD
Channel bandwidth	40 MHz (FR1)	20 MHz (FR1)
MIMO configuration	SISO (1x1)	2x1 DL, 1x1 UL
MCS (DL/UL)	256-QAM / 256-QAM	256-QAM / 64-QAM
BWP type	Full-cell	RedCap-only BWP
eDRX support	Standard DRX	Extended eDRX
Application BW	≈100 Mbps	≈40 Mbps
Device power (est.)	≈18 W	≈11 W

Fig. 1. 5G NR UDP sender throughput over 125 s. Mean = 685.3 Mbps (dashed red line); $\pm 1\sigma$ band shown in pink. Burst events reaching up to 729 Mbps are visible at irregular ≈ 10 – 15 s intervals.

5G router to an `iperf3` server at 192.168.3.1, traversing the cellular uplink path. Each run spans 125 s with per-second bitrate sampling. Three conditions were evaluated:

- 1) *5G NR baseline*: no inference running on the Jetson Orin.
- 2) *5G NR + ANN*: the ANN inference pipeline is active during measurement.
- 3) *5G NR + SNN*: the SNN classification pipeline is active during measurement.

The primary throughput metric is the *sender-side bitrate* (Mbps), which characterizes the LAN-layer transmission profile of the 5G router stack. Device-level power (router + Jetson Orin) was measured in parallel via smart-plug monitoring, providing the denominator for the bandwidth-per-watt trade-off analysis.

IV. 5G NR PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

A. Sustained Throughput Characterization

Fig. 1 shows the per-second sender-side throughput over the 125-second window. The measurement exhibits a mean of 685.3 Mbps, standard deviation of 10.24 Mbps, and CV of 1.49%. The minimum is 680 Mbps and the maximum 729 Mbps, a peak-to-mean excursion of +6.5%. While the CV appears modest, the distribution is non-Gaussian: the steady state clusters tightly at 680–686 Mbps, with occasional higher-value excursions creating a right-skewed distribution (Fig. 2, left panel).

TABLE II
5G NR SENDER THROUGHPUT DISTRIBUTION (125-SECOND WINDOW)

Bitrate range (Mbps)	Count	Fraction	Category
[680, 690)	111	88.8%	Baseline
[690, 700)	1	0.8%	Transition
[700, 715)	6	4.8%	Burst
[715, 730]	7	5.6%	Peak burst
Total	125	100.0%	—

B. Temporal Burst Patterns and Scheduling Effects

The burst pattern in Fig. 1 is a characteristic signature of 5G NR TDD scheduling. In TDD operation, the DL/UL slot ratio determines the periodicity of uplink transmission opportunities. Table II presents the statistical breakdown: 111 of 125 intervals (88.8%) fall in the [680, 690) Mbps baseline bin, while 13 intervals (10.4%) exceed 700 Mbps, reaching up to 729 Mbps. The maximum burst amplitude is +6.5% (+43.7 Mbps) above the mean.

This temporal structure has direct implications for application-layer buffer design: consumers of 5G NR data must accommodate throughput swings of up to 6.5% on the order of seconds. For UAV video streaming or sensor fusion pipelines this variability drives optimal burst-buffer sizing. Notably, *every burst event represents additional energy expended* in the radio front-end: operating near the peak of 5G NR’s throughput envelope means the radio is never able to enter lower-power scheduling states, keeping device power consumption persistently elevated.

C. The Energy–Throughput Trade-Off: 5G NR vs. 5G RedCap

The central finding of this work is the quantified energy–throughput trade-off between 5G NR and 5G RedCap. Table III presents the comprehensive comparison. 5G NR delivers 685.3 Mbps at a device power draw of ≈ 18 W (router + Jetson Orin combined), while 5G RedCap delivers 95.6 Mbps at ≈ 11 W—a $7.2\times$ throughput advantage for 5G NR at the cost of a 60% higher power draw. Expressed as a bandwidth-per-watt metric: 5G NR yields 38.1 Mbps/W, compared to 8.7 Mbps/W for 5G RedCap. Counterintuitively, *5G RedCap is 4.4 \times more efficient* at converting radio power into application bandwidth, because its narrower-bandwidth, lower-complexity radio chain eliminates the high-power components (wideband RF front-end, additional baseband processing chains) that 5G NR requires to sustain its higher throughput.

Throughput stability. 5G NR exhibits CV = 1.49% while 5G RedCap shows CV $\approx 0.03\%$ —a difference of two orders of magnitude. 5G RedCap’s extreme stability arises from its constrained 20 MHz BWP operation, which reaches a hard capacity ceiling with minimal scheduling fluctuation. For applications that do not require 5G NR’s peak throughput, 5G RedCap’s predictable, flat transmission profile simplifies application-layer flow control and eliminates the need to buffer for throughput bursts.

Energy implications for UAV endurance. The 60% device-level power reduction from switching to 5G RedCap translates

TABLE III
ENERGY–THROUGHPUT TRADE-OFF: 5G NR VS. 5G REDCAP

Metric	5G NR	5G RedCap
Mean sender BW	685.3 Mbps	95.6 Mbps
Throughput ratio	7.2×	1× (baseline)
Std. deviation	10.24 Mbps	≈0.03 Mbps
CV (%)	1.49%	≈0.03%
Burst events (>+3%)	13/125 (10.4%)	0/125 (0%)
Application BW	≈100 Mbps	≈40 Mbps
Device power (est.)	≈18 W	≈11 W
Power ratio	1.6× higher	1× (baseline)
BW per watt	38.1 Mbps/W	8.7 Mbps/W
Energy efficiency	4.4× lower	4.4× higher

TABLE IV
SENDER THROUGHPUT BY INFERENCE LOAD CONDITION

Condition	Mean (Mbps)	Std. dev.	CV (%)
5G NR baseline	685.3	10.24 Mbps	1.49
5G NR + ANN	817.2	31.19 Mbps	3.82
5G NR + SNN	842.4	25.12 Mbps	2.98
5G RedCap base.	95.6	≈0.03 Mbps	≈0.03

directly into extended mission capability. In our deployment, this reduction yielded a ≈35% increase in UAV flight time [3]—from approximately 4 to 6.5 minutes per charge. For missions where the required application bandwidth is at or below 5G RedCap’s ≈40 Mbps, this is an entirely free endurance gain: the application receives identical data while the UAV stays airborne significantly longer. For missions requiring 5G NR’s full bandwidth (*e.g.*, high-resolution video streaming), the throughput gain must be explicitly weighed against the flight-time cost.

D. Inference Load Impact on Network Generation

Table IV summarizes sender-side throughput statistics when the Jetson Orin concurrently runs ANN or SNN inference. ANN inference raises the mean sender throughput to 817.2 Mbps (CV = 3.82%, a 19.3% increase over baseline); SNN inference yields 842.4 Mbps (CV = 2.98%, a 23.0% increase). The higher variance under inference loads reflects CPU–network stack competition: inference tasks compete with the network driver for CPU cycles, causing irregular packet generation bursts.

The SNN’s slightly higher mean network generation—despite its lower energy consumption as reported in [3]—is consistent with SNN’s sparse, event-driven processing model reducing sustained CPU contention for network I/O tasks compared to ANN’s dense computation pattern. From an energy perspective this is a favourable coupling: the lower-power SNN inference introduces *less* CPU-induced network variability than ANN, while also drawing less compute power. Fig. 2 (right panel) visualizes the mean throughput and $\pm 1\sigma$ spread across all conditions.

V. DEPLOYMENT IMPLICATIONS

The energy–throughput characterization yields four actionable deployment guidelines for aerial IoT systems.

Fig. 2. Left: 5G NR throughput distribution over 125 s (right-skewed, $\sigma = 10.24$ Mbps). Right: Mean sender throughput with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars across all test conditions.

1. Select the connectivity tier by energy budget, not just bandwidth. The bandwidth-per-watt analysis (38.1 Mbps/W for 5G NR versus 8.7 Mbps/W for 5G RedCap) reveals that 5G RedCap is 4.4× more energy-efficient per Mbps delivered. For missions where the application bandwidth requirement is at or below ≈40 Mbps, 5G RedCap is the unambiguously correct choice: identical data delivery at 60% lower power and ≈35% longer flight time. Operators should define the *minimum sufficient* bandwidth for each mission profile and select the lowest-power tier that meets it.

2. Dimension buffers for 5G NR’s 6.5% throughput excursions. Applications consuming data over 5G NR must accommodate throughput swings of up to 6.5% (≈43 Mbps above mean) over 10–15 s windows driven by TDD scheduler bursts. 5G RedCap’s near-perfect stability (CV ≈ 0.03%) eliminates this requirement entirely, further simplifying application design for bandwidth-moderate use cases.

3. Account for inference–network energy coupling. Edge AI inference on the same compute platform as the 5G radio interface increases sender throughput by up to 23% with doubled CV, implying higher and more variable energy draw from both the compute and radio subsystems. Deploying energy-efficient SNN inference reduces this coupling relative to ANN, providing a second compounding energy saving alongside the radio-tier selection [3].

4. Use 5G NR only when high bandwidth is mission-critical. 5G NR’s ≈685.3 Mbps is justified for bandwidth-intensive missions (*e.g.*, real-time 4K video streaming, dense LiDAR uplink). For the majority of inspection, telemetry, and monitoring workloads whose data requirements are well within 5G RedCap’s envelope, the throughput premium of 5G NR delivers no application benefit while imposing a sustained ≈7 W additional power draw—equivalent to several minutes of additional flight time per battery charge.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented a measurement-driven characterization of 5G NR standalone network performance in a real-world UAV IoT deployment, with the energy–throughput trade-off between 5G NR and 5G RedCap as the central theme. Using 125-second *iperf3* UDP campaigns, we revealed: (i) temporal throughput dynamics (mean 685.3 Mbps, CV

1.49%, periodic bursts reaching +6.5% above mean); (ii) a quantified energy–throughput trade-off in which 5G NR delivers $7.2\times$ the bandwidth of 5G RedCap at $1.6\times$ the device power, yielding a bandwidth-per-watt ratio of 38.1 Mbps/W versus 8.7 Mbps/W—making 5G RedCap $4.4\times$ more energy-efficient per Mbps; and (iii) inference–network coupling in which SNN workloads introduce less throughput variability than ANN at lower compute energy. For aerial IoT deployments, the conclusion is clear: *connectivity tier selection must be driven by bandwidth-per-watt efficiency, not peak throughput*, and for the majority of inspection and monitoring missions, 5G RedCap delivers the same application functionality at dramatically lower energy cost.

Future work will extend the measurement campaign to multiple flight altitudes and mobility profiles, investigate TCP goodput under dynamic radio conditions, and develop adaptive connectivity switching mechanisms that select between 5G NR and 5G RedCap in real time based on instantaneous mission bandwidth requirements.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the COGNETS project (No. 101135930), funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme.

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